

Structural, optical, morphological and organic vapours sensing properties of SnO₂ nanostructures

S. Muthuraja^{*a}, L. Balakrishnan^b, K. Govardhan^a, S. Mohana Roopan^c and S. Manoj Kumaran^a

^aMEMS & Sensors Division, School of Electronics Engineering, VIT University, Vellore-632 014, Tamilnadu, India

E-mail : muthurajas@vit.ac.in

^bMaterials Physics Division, School of Advanced Sciences, VIT University, Vellore-632 014, Tamilnadu, India

^cOrganic Chemistry Division, School of Advanced Sciences, VIT University, Vellore-632 014, Tamilnadu, India

Abstract : Tin oxide is a wide band gap *n*-type semiconductor and has the capability to detect various reducing gases and organic vapours. The sensitivity towards different gases and organic vapours in high temperature environment is already reported. The present work is focused on the development of soft chemical route derived SnO₂ nanostructures to detect organic vapours. The ethanol sensing properties of the derived nanostructures of SnO₂ was analyzed. X-Ray diffraction, UV-Vis spectroscopy, scanning electron microscope and energy dispersive spectroscopy characterizations have been performed to confirm the SnO₂ nanostructure formation. The optimum temperature for sensor operation towards 50 ppm of ethanol has also been found.

Keywords : SnO₂, nanostructure, soft chemical synthesis, ethanol sensing.

Introduction

Tin oxide (SnO₂) is a non-stoichiometric wide band gap (3.6 eV) *n*-type semiconductor. The *n*-type conductivity of the SnO₂ is due to the presence of intrinsic donor defects such as oxygen vacancies (V_O) and tin interstitial (Sn_i). It is a widely used metal oxide semiconductor for wide range of applications due to its excellent chemical, mechanical, electronic, magnetic and optical properties. The nanosized SnO₂ particles can be used in wide range of applications like photoelectronics, chemistry and optics. In addition, it is widely used for gas sensing applications^{1,2}. Volatile gas vapours are found in the enormous fields including food processing, fertilizers, chemical technology and industrial processes. Leakage of such toxic gases is very difficult to trace because they are colourless and non-aromatic in nature¹. The detection of ethanol in trace level is very important as they have variety of negative effects on public health. SnO₂ is highly reactive material for detecting such toxic gases through the chemisorbed oxygen on the surface of the nanoparticle¹. The adsorbed oxygen can capture the electrons from the SnO₂ film/nanostructures, so that they cause a depletion layer

and reduce the conductivity^{2,3}. If the target gas is exposed on the sensor element, the oxygen adsorbates releases the trapped electrons to the conduction band. Hence, the height of the potential barrier in the semiconductor decreases and there by the conductivity increases or the resistance decreases. By this way, we can able to detect and quantify the toxic gases in the atmosphere through calculating the relative change in the resistance.

In this article, we have prepared SnO₂ nanoparticles by soft chemical route. The synthesized SnO₂ nanoparticles were characterized by X-ray diffractometer (XRD), UV-Vis spectrometer, scanning electron microscope (SEM) and energy dispersive spectrometer (EDS). The ethanol sensing characteristics of the prepared SnO₂ nanoparticles were studied at different operating temperatures.

Experimental

Synthesis of SnO₂ nanoparticles :

SnO₂ nanoparticles have been synthesized by soft chemical route³. Initially, SnCl₂.2H₂O (5 g) was dissolved in pure ethanol (100 ml) and the solution was stirred for 3 h. To obtain the precursors to fabricate homogeneous

films, this solution was kept for 24 h at room temperature and the transparent hydrosol was obtained¹⁸.

The obtained hydrosol was dried for 30 min at 100 °C. The derived powder was kept in furnace and heated at 500 °C for 30 min. The resultant powder was analyzed by X-ray diffraction (XRD), UV-Vis spectroscopy, scanning electron microscope (SEM) and energy dispersive spectroscope (EDS) to confirm the SnO₂ nanostructure formation. It was followed by the fabrication of multi-layer films on alumina substrates with dipping and heating procedures for gas sensing study³.

Results and discussion

UV spectroscopy :

UV-Vis spectroscopic characterization was performed using Shimadzu UV-Vis spectrometer to confirm the formation of SnO₂ nanoparticles. The UV-Vis spectrum was recorded in the range of 200–800 nm. Fig. 1 shows the UV-Vis spectrum of the SnO₂ nanoparticles and it shows a strong absorption edge around 224 nm which corresponds SnO₂ nanoparticles⁵. This absorption edge around 224 nm confirms the formation of SnO₂ phase. The inset of Fig. 1 shows the Tauc's plot of the as prepared SnO₂ nanoparticles. The absorption coefficient (α) has been determined from the following formula,

$$\alpha = \frac{2.303}{t} \log_{10} (I/I_0)$$

where, t is the distance travelled by the UV-Vis beam in the cuvette and I/I_0 is the relative intensity of absorbance at a particular wavelength.

Fig. 1. UV absorbance spectroscopy of SnO₂ nanoparticles.

From the plot, the band gap of the prepared SnO₂ nanoparticles has been found as 3.8 eV. The slight blue shift in the band gap is due to the decrease in the size of the SnO₂ grains which leads slight increase in band gap due to quantum confinement effect.

XRD analysis :

The formation of the SnO₂ nanoparticles was further confirmed by the XRD analysis using Bruker D8 Advanced X-ray diffractometer. The XRD pattern of SnO₂ nanoparticles is shown in Fig. 2. It shows diffraction peaks at around 20.5°, 25.4°, 29.8°, 31.7° and 35.4°, and the corresponding d spacing value of SnO₂ nanoparticles were 4.3, 3.5, 2.99, 2.81 and 2.53 nm, respectively^{7,8}.

Fig. 2. XRD patterns of SnO₂ nanoparticles.

The high intensity peak was observed around 25.4°. The XRD pattern confirms that nanoparticles were composed of tetragonal phase SnO₂ nanoparticles which matches well with the JCPDS-041-1445^{5,19}. The average size of the nanoparticle derived from Scherrer's equation matches well with the size, 2–8 nm arrived from particle size analyzer (PSA).

FESEM and EDS analysis :

The morphological feature of SnO₂ nanoparticles were investigated by SEM, equipped with EDS analysis using CARL ZEISS microscope. Fig. 3 shows the SEM micrograph of SnO₂ nanoparticles. The SEM images of SnO₂ nanoparticles exhibit the morphology of very fine flakes with the tiny agglomerates^{10,12}.

The EDS spectrum for the SnO₂ nanostructure also shown in Fig. 3. The pattern depicts the presence of main constituents such as Sn and O. The existence of these atoms may confirm the formation of pure SnO₂ phase.

Fig. 3a. SEM image of the SnO₂ nanostructure.

Fig. 3b. EDAX spectrum of the SnO₂ nanoparticles.

Fabrication of SnO₂ gas sensor :

The gas sensing was performed by coating the paste of calcinated SnO₂ powder mixed with PVA (polyvinyl alcohol) onto a Al₂O₃ tube having the dimensions of 23 cm in length, 6 cm in external diameter and 2.5 cm in internal diameter¹². The electrical contact to the coating was given through platinum wires²⁴. Before going to the sensor study, the sensing element was heated at high temperature which makes the PVA to decompose and increase markedly the contact strength³.

Fig. 4 shows the schematic of the sensor element used for the present study. A heating element made up of microme wire was placed inside the tube to maintain the operating temperature between room temperature and 400 °C. The temperature was maintained by proportional, integral and derivative (PID) controller. A circuit voltage of $V_C = 10$ V was supplied across the sensors and the load resistor ($R_L = 10$ k) connected in series. The signal voltage across the load, which changed with sort and in the presence of target gas was measured. The sensitivity

Fig. 4a. Schematic diagram of the sensor element.

Fig. 4b. Image of the fabricated sensor element.

of the sensor for different operating temperature was measured by measuring the resistance of the sensor element in air and target gas ambience¹². The gas sensitivity (S) is calculated as the ratio of the change of resistance in presence of gas (R_g) to that in air (R_a) from the below formula,

$$S = R_a/R_g$$

Gas sensing mechanism :

The conductivity of metal oxide semiconductors changes according to gas concentration. The adsorption/desorption of oxygen species on the surface of the sensing material is reacting with the analyzing gases and causing the conductivity changes. The reaction organic vapours or target gas with the above said oxygen species will cause the change in resistance. Chemisorption of O²⁻, O₂⁻ and O⁻ covers the surface and creates the space charge region and the exposure of ethanol reacts with these oxygen species, especially O⁻ which is highly active and dominant in SnO₂ at the temperature ranges from 422 K to 933 K and causes release of electron. This has been ex-

plained through the following reactions,

Through these reactions the chemisorption of oxygen is taking place on the surface of the sensor element.

Sensing chamber :

The sophisticated sensing chamber designed for high temperature sensor studies has 15 ml of volume. It has 3 inlets for multiple gas testing purpose (Fig. 5). There is a PID controlled heater and substrate holder for thin film sensor measurement is placed inside the chamber. In the present investigation, the heater itself acts as the sample holder which suits for different types of base substrates like tube, matrix plates, etc. The chamber is made with stainless steel and the heater also with the same metal to conduct the elevated temperatures. An air tight septum is used to keep the vacuum condition throughout the sensor studies and inject the vapors to the sensor chamber using syringe.

Sensor studies and results :

The sensor studies were carried out by placing the sensor element inside the chamber on heater. The sensing response was recorded using an electrometer by the injection of 50 ppm of ethanol by commercial syringe for various temperatures.

Fig. 5a. Sensor element holder/heater.

Fig. 5b. Sensing chamber with PID controller.

Fig. 6 shows the temperature dependent gas sensing characteristics of SnO₂ nanostructures. It is seen that the sensitivity of the films increases with increase in operating temperature due to the high activation energy and enhanced catalytic reaction process because of the change in oxidation of the chemisorbed oxygen²⁵. Further, after a particular temperature the sensitivity of the film decreases due to the desorption of oxygen²⁵. A higher value of sensitivity has been observed for the synthesized SnO₂ nanostructures at 250 °C¹⁴⁻¹⁶. In addition, the response kinetics of the SnO₂ nanostructure sensor has also been measured at 250 °C (Fig. 7).

Fig. 6. Temperature vs sensitivity for 50 ppm of ethanol.

Fig. 7. Time vs sensitivity for 50 ppm of ethanol.

The figure implies that the SnO₂ nanostructures have fast response and retrace times. The response and retrace times have been observed around 30 s. These results confirm that the SnO₂ nanostructure based sensor has good ability to trace out ethanol very quickly at 250 °C^{21,22}.

Conclusion

SnO₂ nanoparticles were synthesized through a simplest soft chemical route. The synthesized SnO₂ nanostructures have been characterized by XRD, UV-Vis spectroscopy, SEM and EDS. These studies confirm the formation of tetragonal structured SnO₂ nanoparticles. The fabricated SnO₂ nanoparticles based thick film sensor element was tested for 50 ppm of ethanol vapors at different temperatures. From the sensing analysis, it has been found that the sensor has optimum sensing temperature at 250 °C with fast response and retrace time.

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